

Evaluating Strategies for Automatically Detecting the Long Continuing Current Signatures on Electric Field Waveforms of Lightning Events Occurring in the Metropolitan Area of Belo Horizonte

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Abstract— This paper discusses the results of a computational approach in Python for automatically detecting Long Continuing Currents (LCCs) in lightning data measured in the metropolitan region of Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais. The authors developed a computational routine to reliably output LCC characteristics, such as initial and final time, duration and amplitude variation per time. This method enables fast, accurate identification of severe LCCs in large datasets to support statistical analysis. The results show positive responses from the code for the cases of negative and positive LCC analyzed but show challenges to be considered for a perfect evaluation.

Keywords— lightning; long continuing current; electric field waveforms; lightning activity in Brazil; lightning location system; python code.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lightning can be classified in various ways, according to the different aspects or viewpoints considered for analyzing the phenomenon [1]. Atmospheric discharges are primarily categorized into two main groups – cloud lightning and cloud-to-ground lightning (CG) – based on the region across which they develop.

Cloud-to-ground discharges are generally considered the most critical lightning type for society, as it can produce the most severe and deleterious effects, such as direct and indirect impacts on humans [2], large wildfires [3], [4], [5], [6], rupture of cables in transmission lines [7], [8], damage to residential buildings and wind turbines [9], [10], and even the loss of human and animal life. They can be further classified according to the direction of leader development and the polarity of the

charge transferred to the ground. If the plasma leader initiates in the cloud and terminates at ground, this lightning flash is classified as a downward lightning. Conversely, if the plasma leader originates from a protruding structure and propagates towards the clouds for several milliseconds, it is considered an upward lightning. Both upward and downward lightning can be also categorized as either positive or negative, depending on the polarity of the charge transferred to the ground [1].

Literature identifies three possible modes of charge transfer to the ground during CG [11], [12], all of which have been observed in both upward and downward flashes: i) the leader/return stroke sequence, (ii) the continuing current, and (3) the M-component mode of charge transfer. Each of these modes presents its own typical current parameters and they are usually associated with one or more specific kinds of damage caused to power systems.

The continuing current (CC) is a mode of charge transfer that occurs in approximately 10-30% of CG lightning return strokes [2], [13], [14], [15]. It is characterized by a persistent luminosity of the lightning channel, observed hundreds of microseconds after the attachment. This luminosity is attributed to the continuous flow of a low-level current through the channel, typically ranging from tens to hundreds of amperes, and with total duration ranging up to several hundreds of milliseconds. This sustained current flow is responsible for transferring a substantial amount of charge to the strike point. The large heat transfer at this point associated with the flow of the continuing current can subject the affected structure to intense thermal effects, increasing the likelihood of severe damage and the potential for ignition.

Continuing current are usually categorized into three groups: (a) very short continuing currents (VSCC), which last from 1 to 10 milliseconds; (b) short continuing currents (SCC), which last between 10 and 40 milliseconds; and (c) long continuing currents, which remain active for more than 40 milliseconds (LCC) [16], [17], [18], [19].

LCCs are especially critical for structures and objects at ground level due to the highly severe thermal effects they can produce. The flow of CCs along the composite material of wind turbine blades, for example, can result in permanent damage [20], [21], [22]. Furthermore, optical fiber ground wires (OPGW) in overhead powerlines are prone to strand fractures and potential breakage caused by these current components [7], [8]. Recent investigations have also explored the significant potential of CCs to ignite large-scale wildfires in countries such as United States, Canada and Australia [5], [23], [24].

The remote detection of these current components can be primarily performed from the corresponding electric field waveforms measured at ground level. In this context, Figure 1 exhibits a typical e-field profile of a long continuing current measured in Florida on July 27, 1979. This flash presented four strokes, and right after the impulsive phase of the 3rd stroke, a long continuing current (LCC) was measured, which is depicted by the continuous growth of the electric field intensity. This signature is associated with a charge transfer to soil occurring at an approximately constant rate.

Figure 1 - Electric field of a 4-strokes negative CG flash event containing a typical signature of continuing current after the third stroke, measured in Florida on July 27, 1979, at 22:40:14 UTC and at 6.5 km from the measurement point [1].

The primary objective of this work is to introduce a methodology for the automated detection LCC in electric field measurements obtained from a novel lightning detection network installed in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte, Brazil. To accomplish this goal, Section II provides a detailed overview of the deployed instrumentation, Section III outlines the key aspects of the adopted methodology for the automated detection of LCC, the main results and findings are presented in Section IV, and the final remarks and concluding points are summarized in Section V.

II. INSTRUMENTATION

The data utilized in this study was acquired by a novel network installed in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte, Brazil, during the 2023-2024 local thunderstorm season. Figure 2 illustrates the 5 sensors covering the Belo Horizonte metropolitan area, with an additional sixth detector located in Curvelo, primarily used for testing purposes.

Figure 2 - Location of the five HRL™ Detectors in the metropolitan area of Belo Horizonte. It can be observed that the five stations compose a network that is capable of satisfactorily covering the metropolitan area of the city. The average distance between the stations is around 25 km. Adapted from Google Maps.

The network's sensors consist of proprietary Fire Neural Network instrumentation, the "FNN HRL™ Detector", two of which are illustrated in Figure 3. Each sensor has two concentric plate antennas feeding two measurement channels: the High Frequency (HF) channel for recording faster electric field changes from return strokes and cloud pulses, and the Low Frequency (LF) channel for slower variations associated with continuing charge transfer, including LCC signatures. The sensors are GPS-synchronized, enabling high-resolution temporal data for lightning location using techniques like Time Difference of Arrival (TDoA).

Figure 3 – FNN HRL™ Detector installed at (a) the Nova Gameleira campus of CEFET-MG and (b) the Ribeirão das Neves campus of IFMG.

III. METHODOLOGY

During a single thunderstorm, a significant number of lightning return strokes can be detected. For comprehensive characterization of the parameters associated with each lightning event, it is desirable to have mechanisms for automated computation of these parameters. Under this perspective, this section describes the initial development of an automated tool for calculating the duration of LCCs in measurements obtained from the novel lightning detection network of Belo Horizonte.

The strategy used for automatically detecting LCCs involves identifying the linear pattern that continuing current components tend to produce in electric field waveforms. Given that the current associated with LCCs is approximately constant and long-lasting, its signature becomes clearer in the records of electric field changes of the LF channel as a constant increase, as depicted in Figure 1.

To detect this linear increase in the e-field waveforms, a moving window approach was adopted in the development of a post-processing Python code. Figure 4 illustrates how the data vector is swept during the search for LCC patterns. The e-field data of the LF channel, with a total of N points, is divided into smaller sections or "windows" of length " w ". A sweep is performed along the data points, and in each step, the relevant features of the current window under evaluation are calculated according to a pre-defined metric. The resulting analysis allows identifying signatures of LCCs. It is worth noting that the window length " w " is set as a direct fraction of the sample rate of the measured signal.

Figure 4 – Application of the developed Python algorithm for automatically detecting LCCs

IV. RESULTS

To systematically illustrate the application of the developed tool, two events with LCCs are presented and discussed. The developed algorithm outputs several information, the most important ones being:

- Initial time*: when the LCC event started, expressed in ms.
- Final time*: when the LCC event ended, expressed in ms.
- LCC duration*: the total duration of the event, also expressed in ms.
- dY/dX*: the ratio between the e-field variation (in relative units) and the total duration of the LCC.

In addition to the quantitative results, visualizing the detected LCC waveform and corresponding parameters is important for evaluating the performance of the implemented algorithm. In this perspective, the code was set to graphically mark the initial and final limits of each identified LCC with an 'x' and bound the total interval with a dashed line. Furthermore, the corresponding HF measurements are included to support the visualization of the flash overall features in which the LCC occurred.

A. Negative LCCs

The first analyzed event occurred on February 4, 2024, at 20:04:57 (UTC). It is a negative polarity LCC recorded by the FNN HRL™ Detectors installed in Betim (Fig 5a), Ribeirão das Neves (Fig 5b), and Sabará (Fig 5c). The corresponding *Initial time*, *Final time*, *LCC duration* and *dY/dX* values presented in Table I.

TABLE I
RESULTS FOR A NEGATIVE LCC MEASURED IN 3 DIFFERENT STATIONS

Station	Initial time [ms]	Final time [ms]	LCC duration [ms]	$\frac{dY}{dX}$ [unit/ms]
Betim	488.535	576.836	188.301	0.310
Sabará	490.990	704.742	213.752	0.027
Ribeirão das Neves	487.620	689.572	201.952	0.035

The visual inspection of the plots presented in Figure 5, as well as the analysis of the output provided in Table I, confirm the good performance of the code. It accurately located the initiation of the LCC immediately after the impulsive phase of the second return stroke, as evident in the HF signals. The time boundaries of the LCC were also well identified. The variations in LCC initial times across the stations are attributed to the different propagation delays of the electric field wave to each measurement location. Similarly, the differences in LCC durations are due to the variable attenuation of the static electric field component as the associated electromagnetic wave propagates. Despite these spatial dependencies, the consistency in the temporal characteristics enables the use of Time Difference of Arrival localization techniques.

B. Positive LCCs

A similar analysis is presented in the following lines for a positive LCC that occurred on January 31, 2024, at 20:08:01 (UTC), Figure 6, and was recorded by the detectors installed in Betim and Ribeirão das Neves. As depicted in Table II, in which the corresponding parameters are presented, the start times showed a minimal variation of nearly 4.8 milliseconds, while the durations differed by only 17.2 milliseconds.

Given this proximity in terms of duration, it can be stated that the Ribeirão das Neves station was closer to the event, as indicated by a higher rate of change dY/dX , which can be validated by observing the greater amplitude recorded at this station, reaching a bit more than -70 units.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5 - Identification results via Python code of the same negative long continuing current occurring on February 4, 2024, at 20:04:57 (UTC), which was recorded by three measurement stations located in Betim (a), Ribeirão das Neves (b), and Sabará (c).

TABLE II
RESULTS FOR A POSITIVE LCC MEASURED IN 2 DIFFERENT STATIONS

Station	Initial time [ms]	Final time [ms]	LCC duration [ms]	$\frac{dY}{dX}$ [unit/ms]
Betim	553.488	693.229	139.801	0.070
Ribeirão das Neves	548.736	705.737	157.001	0.454

(a)

(b)

Figure 6 - Identification results via Python code, now, for the same positive long continuing current occurring on January 31, 2024, at 20:08:01 (UTC), which was recorded by three measurement stations located in Betim (a), Ribeirão das Neves (b), only.

V. FINAL REMARKS

The obtained results demonstrate the preliminary effectiveness of the developed algorithm in identifying the linear behavior characteristic of LCCs. The algorithm has been applied to multiple cases, with an ongoing statistical analysis of the 2023-2024 thunderstorm season data.

Future efforts should evaluate the integration of additional techniques alongside the existing Python-based code for LCC identification. This includes incorporating HF measurements in parallel with the LF data, as well as correlating the responses across multiple stations to precisely delineate the LCC interval. One potential avenue is the use of artificial intelligence tools, though this would require a substantial validated dataset - a limitation given the recent January 2024 installation of the measurement network at the end of the thunderstorm season in Brazil.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support and resources provided by the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG) for this research project. Additionally, the authors are grateful for the financial support received from the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG) through grant number PCE-00106-24.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. A. Rakov and M. A. Uman, *Lightning: Physics and Effects*. Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [2] V. Cooray, *An Introduction to Lightning*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2015. doi: 10.1007/978-94-017-8938-7.
- [3] O. Pinto Neto, I. R. C. A. Pinto, O. Pinto Junior, and E. R. Williams, "Evidence of a link between Amazon fires and lightning," *J Atmos Sol Terr Phys*, vol. 249, p. 106095, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jastp.2023.106095.
- [4] A. Krause, S. Kloster, S. Wilkenskjeld, and H. Paeth, "The sensitivity of global wildfires to simulated past, present, and future lightning frequency," *J Geophys Res Biogeosci*, vol. 119, no. 3, pp. 312–322, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1002/2013JG002502.
- [5] F. J. Pérez-Invernón *et al.*, "Lightning-ignited wildfires and long continuing current lightning in the Mediterranean Basin: preferential meteorological conditions," *Atmos Chem Phys*, vol. 21, no. 23, pp. 17529–17557, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.5194/acp-21-17529-2021.
- [6] V. Schumacher, A. Setzer, M. M. F. Saba, K. P. Naccarato, E. Mattos, and F. Justino, "Characteristics of lightning-caused wildfires in central Brazil in relation to cloud-ground and dry lightning," *Agric For Meteorol*, vol. 312, p. 108723, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.agrformet.2021.108723.
- [7] R. Yang, X. Shu, L. Wu, Y. Quan, and H. Liu, "Analysis on Lightning Strike Breaking Defects of 500kV Yangdong Line II Optical Cable," *J Phys Conf Ser*, vol. 1865, no. 2, p. 022030, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1865/2/022030.
- [8] W. A. Chisholm, J. P. Levine, and P. Chowdhuri, "Lightning arc damage to optical fiber ground wires (OPGW): parameters and test methods," in *2001 Power Engineering Society Summer Meeting. Conference Proceedings (Cat. No.01CH37262)*, IEEE, 2001, pp. 88–93 vol.1. doi: 10.1109/PESS.2001.969990.
- [9] F. Rachidi *et al.*, "A Review of Current Issues in Lightning Protection of New-Generation Wind-Turbine Blades," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 2489–2496, Jun. 2008, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2007.896443.
- [10] "IEC 62305 - Protection Against Lightning." IEC, Geneva, 2010.
- [11] M. Azadifar, M. Rubinstein, Q. Li, F. Rachidi, and V. Rakov, "A New Engineering Model of Lightning M Component That Reproduces Its Electric Field Waveforms at Both Close and Far Distances," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 124, no. 24, pp. 14008–14023, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1029/2019JD030796.
- [12] V. A. Rakov, D. E. Crawford, K. J. Rambo, G. H. Schnetzer, M. A. Uman, and R. Thottappillil, "M-component mode of charge transfer to ground in lightning discharges," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 106, no. D19, pp. 22817–22831, Oct. 2001, doi: 10.1029/2000JD000243.
- [13] V. A. Rakov, *Fundamentals of Lightning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016. doi: 10.1017/CBO9781139680370.
- [14] M. A. Ferro, M. M. F. Saba, and O. Pinto, "Continuing current in multiple channel cloud-to-ground lightning," *Atmos Res*, vol. 91, no. 2–4, pp. 399–403, Feb. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.atmosres.2008.04.011.
- [15] C. W. C4.407, *Lightning Parameters for Engineering Applications*. CIGRE, 2013.
- [16] T. Shindo and M. A. Uman, "Continuing current in negative cloud-to-ground lightning," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 94, no. D4, pp. 5189–5198, Apr. 1989, doi: 10.1029/JD094iD04p05189.
- [17] M. Brook, N. Kitagawa, and E. J. Workman, "Quantitative study of strokes and continuing currents in lightning discharges to ground," *J Geophys Res*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 649–659, Feb. 1962, doi: 10.1029/JZ067i002p00649.
- [18] N. Kitagawa, M. Brook, and E. J. Workman, "Continuing currents in cloud-to-ground lightning discharges," *J Geophys Res*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 637–647, Feb. 1962, doi: 10.1029/JZ067i002p00637.
- [19] M. M. F. Saba, M. G. Ballarotti, and O. Pinto, "Negative cloud-to-ground lightning properties from high-speed video observations," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 111, no. D3, Feb. 2006, doi: 10.1029/2005JD006415.
- [20] A. Smorgonskiy, F. Rachidi, M. Rubinstein, N. V. Korovkin, and A. P. Vassilopoulos, "Are Standardized Lightning Current Waveforms Suitable for Aircraft and Wind Turbine Blades Made of Composite Materials?," *IEEE Trans Electromagn Compat*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 1320–1328, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TEMC.2017.2682324.
- [21] J. Montanyà *et al.*, "Global distribution of winter lightning: a threat to wind turbines and aircraft," *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 1465–1472, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.5194/nhess-16-1465-2016.
- [22] CIGRE WG C4.409, "Lightning Protection of Wind Turbine Blades," *CIGRE technical brochure*. CIGRE, 2014.
- [23] F. J. Pérez-Invernón *et al.*, "On the Role of Continuing Currents in Lightning-Induced Fire Ignition," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 128, no. 21, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1029/2023JD038891.
- [24] C. J. Schultz, N. J. Nauslar, J. B. Wachter, C. R. Hain, and J. R. Bell, "Spatial, Temporal and Electrical Characteristics of Lightning in Reported Lightning-Initiated Wildfire Events," *Fire*, vol. 2, no. 2, p. 18, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.3390/fire2020018.